

Statement by editors of academic journals
in the field of actuarial science

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We endorse the following general principle:

The production of new knowledge is a collective human achievement built on identifiable creativity and effort. The use of artificial intelligence tools must not obscure or appropriate human authorship, but instead act as a transparent intermediary that honours and verifies the human origins of scientific and technical innovation.

Any AI-assisted output should trace and credit the underlying work of researchers, inventors, and sources on which it relies. Giving full, transparent, and accurate credit enables the recognition and accountability of knowledge creators and the integrity of the research process, as it builds on existing work.

Fair recognition of authorship is fundamental for the operation of our knowledge ecosystem and this places specific and evolving responsibilities on all stakeholders, including journal editors, AI platforms, publishers, authors and reviewers.

Andreas Tsanakas, City St George's, University of London; Editor-in-Chief, *Annals of Actuarial Science*.

Adrian O'Hagan, University College Dublin; Editor, *British Actuarial Journal*.

Hansjörg Albrecher, University of Lausanne; Editor-in-Chief, *European Actuarial Journal*.

Andrew Cairns, Heriot-Watt University, and Roger Laeven, University of Amsterdam; Editors, *Insurance: Mathematics and Economics*.

Montserrat Guillen, University of Barcelona; Editor, *North American Actuarial Journal*.

Boualem Djehiche, KTH-Royal Institute of Technology; Editor-in-Chief, *Scandinavian Actuarial Journal*.